

THE USE OF MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF MUSICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of interactive technologies allows not only to diversify the forms of lessons, but also significantly improve the results of the studied material. Students are very interested in such forms of work. Lessons using interactive technologies allow the teacher to see some students and their individual characteristics in a new way. In this article, the author provides extensive information on the use of modern interactive methods in the process of musical education.

Keywords: interactive methods; educational conditions; personnel training; innovative technologies; educational effectiveness; modern pedagogy; optimization; topicality; interactive education; cognitive activity; the essence of interactive education; passive methods; mastery; opportunity; favorable environment; exchange; mental activity; reflective activity; visual-auditory; motor-auditory; musical-game; principle; project; universal; personal; educational models

INTRODUCTION

Interactive forms and methods are innovative and help to activate the cognitive activity of students in music lessons, to independently perceive musical material. They help to solve the problems of aesthetic and moral education, to form the creative activity of students in curricular and extracurricular activities.

The use of interactive teaching methods in the practice of music teaching helps to increase the intellectual activity of students, and therefore the effectiveness of the lesson. Even the most passive students are enthusiastically involved in active classes, where they develop the skills of original thinking and a creative approach to solving problems.

The main part.

Possibilities of using interactive methods in music lessons. We live in a rapidly developing society. In this regard, special requirements are placed on the education system. Recently, great attention has been paid to the introduction of innovative technologies in education and personnel training in order to improve the quality of education, create favorable learning conditions with the active interaction of all students.

The factors determining the effectiveness of education are the ability to work with information and independently organize cognitive activity. This task is especially relevant for the teacher, who must organize such activities for students. With the use of new technologies, teaching methods are also changing.

Modern pedagogy uses interactive methods that help optimize the learning process for schoolchildren. The insufficient development of the use of interactive methods in music education determines its relevance.

The relevance of this problem is also associated with the contradiction between the social order of educating a creative, active member of society and the real superiority of traditional methods of transferring ready-made knowledge to students in school education. We see the solution to this contradiction in the development and use of interactive methods that reflect the specifics of students' musical and educational activities in music lessons.

The State Educational Standard requires students to achieve meta-subject, subject and personal results. If meta-subject and subject results can be obtained partially by transferring ready-made information, then personal educational results are possible only through the use of interactive methods and forms, in which each student has the opportunity to independently express his opinion, acquire knowledge, and actively participate in the formation of their skills.

Interactive education, according to Andrey Pometun and Leonid Pirozhenko, is a specific form of organizing cognitive activity, which has a specific purposeful goal - to create comfortable learning conditions in which each student should feel successful, intellectually capable, which will make the learning process effective.

Cognitive activity. A person constantly studies the world around him, observes, is engaged in self-education, studies at school or university. Human cognitive activity is purposeful and systematic. Let's find out in more detail what features cognitive activity has.

The essence of interactive education is that the teacher's activity gives way to the activity of students, but the role of the teacher does not decrease, but rather increases. The teacher must be proactive, and the student must manage his own knowledge, choose the trajectory of learning, the pace of learning.

The range of modern teaching methods and technologies is extremely wide. In pedagogy, there are many, interconnected classifications of teaching methods. Traditionally, they are divided into passive, active and interactive methods.

1. Passive methods are a form of interaction between students and teachers, in which the teacher plays the role of the main actor and manager of the lesson, and students play the role of passive listeners. In passive lessons, communication between the teacher and students is carried out through surveys, independent work, tests, tests, etc. From the point of view of modern pedagogical technologies and the effectiveness of students' mastering of educational material, the passive method is considered the most ineffective, but nevertheless it has its advantages. This is the possibility of presenting a large amount of educational material in a limited time frame of the lesson, as well as relatively quick preparation for the lesson by an experienced teacher. Therefore, many teachers prefer the passive method to other methods. The lecture is the most common type of passive lesson. This type of lesson is widespread in higher

education institutions, where adults, well-rounded individuals who have set clear goals for in-depth study of the subject study.

2. Active methods are a form of active interaction between students and teachers, in which they are on equal terms. Many equate active and interactive methods, but despite their commonality, they differ. Interactive methods can be considered the most modern form of active methods.

3. Interactive methods ("inter" - mutual, "act" - action) - mean interaction, being in a conversational mode, talking with someone. Unlike active methods, interactive ones are aimed at a wider interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other and at the predominance of student activity in the learning process. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons is to direct the activities of students to achieve the goals of the lesson. The teacher also develops a lesson plan (usually interactive exercises and tasks, during which the student studies the material). Therefore, the main components of interactive lessons are interactive exercises and tasks that students complete. An important difference between interactive exercises and tasks from ordinary ones is that by completing them, students do not only consolidate the studied material, but also independently learn new ones.

Sergey Semyonovich Kashlev classifies interactive methods according to their leading function in pedagogical interaction at each stage :

- Methods of creating a favorable environment, as a result of which trusting relationships are established with each other;
- Methods of organizing the exchange of activities, uniting students into creative groups for joint activities;
- Methods of organizing mental activity and creating meaning perform a leading function: the creation of new content, their individual meaning by students and teachers, the exchange of these meanings, the enrichment of their individual semantic experience;
- Methods of organizing reflective activity are aimed at self-analysis of the participants' own activities, their results, and recording the state of development.

The methodology of interactive music teaching is based on the system of principles developed in music pedagogy by B.V. Asafiev, B. L. Yavorsky, N. Bryusova; about the creative heritage by K.N. Igumnov, G.G. Neuhaus, about the concept of art education by D.B. Kabalevsky, B.M. Nemensky, L.V. Goryunova and others.

In the system of music education, it is necessary to talk about the methods of visual-auditory, motor-auditory, musical-game teaching in teaching with interactive methods.

□ Visual-auditory method - is implemented in the process of the student's interaction with a musical work. In terms of content, this method is based on the "music observation method" formulated by B. Asafiev, which forms the ability to meaningfully perceive through observing and mastering changes in the intonation of a musical work.

□ Motor-auditory method - is aimed at the development of musical and plastic activity. Music and plastic arts have a common intonation basis. As in music, intonation is a carrier of meaning in the art of movement. But if in music this is musical intonation, then in the art of movement it is rhythmic-plastic intonation. Therefore, the features of

musical-plastic activity are based on the nature of the relationship between musical and rhythmic-plastic intonations.

□ The musical-game method is a synthesis of musical, plastic and theatrical movements. This method is expressed not only in various genres of choreographic art, but also in dramatic works.

Interactive technologies provide various forms of organizing student interaction in educational activities: work in pairs, small and large groups using the project method. In musical culture lessons in a secondary school, it is appropriate to alternate the listed forms of joint activity of students depending on the didactic and educational tasks set for the development of communication and interaction skills. Group and collective work naturally arise in the performance of folk rituals, in the process of staging theatrical dialogues.

We note that gradually, from class to class, the share of group work increases, as students learn to work in a team and acquire basic communication skills. Working in groups helps to develop tolerance, collectivism and mutual assistance in students, which stimulates the process of artistic knowledge;

The main principle of organizing interactive interaction in the music education system is the equality of all components of the educational process, which allows combining traditionalism and innovation in the pedagogical process and directing it towards the personal growth and creative self-development of students. In today's conditions. In interactive learning conditions, attention is paid to the independent educational activities of students, which contributes to the fuller self-realization of schoolchildren in the educational process, and therefore to its effectiveness.

Interactive teaching methods have gone through a long process of development. The main requirement of the humanistic idea is to ensure the unity of pedagogical interaction based on didactic principles and the internal state of the self-developing student, which is consistent with new methods of organizing the pedagogical process.

The project method is used at the stages of introducing the topic (mainly informational type), revealing the main content of the topic (research and information types), generalizing the topic (game or artistic-creative types). When organizing small and large groups, it is advisable to take into account the individual abilities and aesthetic interests of students, their previous artistic experience and knowledge of various types of art.

In connection with the introduction of the State Educational Standard for General Secondary Education of the New Generation, new approaches to teaching the subject of Musical Culture are needed. Personal, subject and meta-subject requirements for the student are presented for better mastering the basic educational program by students.

To achieve high results in education, the program has developed universal educational activities. The work in the lesson should be carried out in such a way that the student does not accept knowledge in a ready-made form, but tries to find new things and is able to think. For this purpose, the new generation standards have created several personal, cognitive and regulatory types of universal actions.

These trends require a change in the strategy of educating and training the younger generation. There is a great interest in updating educational models, technologies and methods. Currently, creative groups have developed educational and

methodological collections in the subject of Music Culture, which include textbooks and creative notebooks for students. This helps to deeply master their content. Also, special attention is paid to pedagogical innovations, the introduction of interactive technologies for teaching music.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to note that the use of interactive teaching methods in music teaching methodology serves to increase the intellectual activity of students, and therefore the effectiveness of the lesson. Even the most passive students are enthusiastically involved in active classes, in which they develop original thinking and creative approaches to solving problems. In addition, all the basic competencies are formed:

- the ability to take responsibility in decision-making;
- tolerance, respect for other people's opinions;
- the ability to work with different types of information;
- the ability to constantly improve one's knowledge, etc.

The main thing is that the use of interactive methods helps to form an emotionally mature person, capable of independent thinking and decision-making.

The use of interactive technologies allowed not only to diversify the forms of lessons, but also to significantly improve the results of the studied material. Students showed great interest in such forms of work. Lessons using interactive technologies allow the teacher to see some students and their individual characteristics in a new way. Having a choice in the options for completing homework activates students and allows them to choose the task that is most interesting for them, which means that the result of mastering the material can be much higher.

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